

ISic0704

Funerary inscription of Gaius Iulius Eutyclus

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 169

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth 4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30-35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. D (is) M (anibus) s (acrum)
2. C (aius) Iulius Eutychn
3. us vixit an (nos) XXXX
4. uxor b (ene) mer (enti) fec (it)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Gaius Iulius Eutychnus lived for 40 years.
His wife made this
for a well deserving man.

Translation (it)

Consacrato agli Dei Mani | Caius Iulius Eutychnus | Visse per 40 anni | La moglie
pose per (il marito)
meritevole

Commentary

Whether Gaius Iulius Eutyclus was a freedman (former slave) or freeborn we cannot tell, but the absence of a father's name perhaps suggests the former. The Greek name Εὐτύχης ('good fortune') is very common, in Sicily and across the Greek world. The inscription follows a very standard form for Latin epitaphs.

Digital identifiers:

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EDR 081509

EDCS 6100269

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0341g

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 97

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